

PERIODONTALLY INVOLVED ROOT SURFACES BIOCOMPATIBILITY FOLLOWING APPLICATION OF DIFFERENT CURCUMIN CONCENTRATION (IN VITRO STUDY)

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Abstract

Objectives: This study was designed to evaluate the effect of 0.12 %, 1 % and 2 % curcumin concentrations on PDL cell adhesion to periodontally affected root surfaces. **Material and methods:** 20 periodontally affected teeth which were extracted and sectioned into root samples. PDL fibroblasts were collected from freshly extracted teeth for orthodontic reasons and were cultured and incubated, PDL fibroblast cells were added to curcumin coated root samples in different concentrations Study samples were divided into 4 groups: Group 1 (0.12% of curcumin paste), Group 2 (1% curcumin paste), Group 3 (2% curcumin paste) and Group 4 (control group). All samples were investigated by scanning electron microscope. **Results:** Group 3 of 2% curcumin concentration showed well defined multilayered adherent cells covering the entire surface with totally flat polyhedral bodies with long cytoplasmic extensions and little or no bacterial colonization or sporadic separate planktonic bacterial adhesion. **Conclusion:** Curcumin 2% provides the optimal stimulation of cellular attachment and antibacterial effects over periodontitis affected root surfaces.

Keywords: Periodontal Ligament Fibroblast, Curcumin Concentration, Root Surface.

INTRODUCTION

Periodontal disease is a chronic inflammatory disease of supporting tissues surrounding the tooth. It is considered as one of the most concerning global oral health burdens affecting almost 10-15% of world's population and 89.8% of Egyptian population (1, 2). Pathogenic anaerobic microflora adhering to the tooth surfaces have been recognized as the causative agents of periodontitis. Apical migration of epithelial attachment, connective

tissue breakdown, alveolar bone loss and eventually tooth loss are common sequelae of periodontitis if left untreated⁽³⁾. The principal cells in periodontal ligaments (PDLs) are the fibroblasts (PDLFs are responsible for the synthesis of collagen bundles in the PDL in addition to renewal and replacement of old and damaged collagen fibrils^(4,5). Fibroblast contributes to periodontal tissue homeostasis by their ability to remodel tissues and to repopulate wounds^(6,7). For successful periodontal therapy and predictable regeneration, the presence of viable and healthy cells of the periodontium is essential and these cells should adhere to the root surfaces of the teeth⁽⁸⁾. Lucas et al.⁽⁹⁾ suggested that endotoxins from periodontal pathogens penetrate the root surface and inhibit cellular attachment. Bacterial endotoxin adsorbed to dental surfaces inhibited cell attachment to dental surfaces. Moreover, elimination of bacterial endotoxins had improved human gingival fibroblasts cellular attachment⁽¹⁰⁾.

Herbal extracts have been used to cure human illness for ages. Several herbal formulations have the capacity to control production of pro-inflammatory mediators thereby managing many inflammatory processes⁽¹¹⁾. Curcumin has strong antibacterial activity which suppresses the growth of diverse types of gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria^(12, 13). Curcumin is a natural extract with antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties⁽¹⁴⁾.

To the best of our knowledge, no study has been performed to investigate the effect of different curcumin concentrations on the attachment of human periodontal ligament fibroblasts to periodontally diseased roots. The present study was performed to determine the attachment of PDL cells to the diseased roots modified by different concentration of curcumin as a primary outcome. Secondary outcome was the effect of different curcumin concentration on bacterial colonization over periodontally affected root surfaces.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Participants for this study were recruited by screening patients receiving treatment at the outpatient clinic of the Department of Oral Medicine and Periodontology at the Faculty of Dentistry, October 6 University. Each patient received a detailed explanation of the research procedures and signed an informed consent form allowing the use of their extracted teeth in the study. The study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee at the Faculty of Dentistry, October 6 University, Giza, Egypt, with approval number RECO6U/25-2022.

Following a diagnosis of stage IV periodontitis, 20 periodontally involved human anterior and posterior teeth with grade III mobility were collected from 20 patients (16 males and 4 females, aged 41 to 54 years). The study excluded patients with systemic disorders affecting the periodontium, smokers, and pregnant women. Additionally, patients who had undergone scaling, root planing, or dental prophylaxis in the previous three months were excluded. Each patient provided one caries-free tooth that was scheduled for extraction as part of their dental treatment. In addition, ten impacted third molars, extracted from medically healthy adolescents, were used to obtain periodontal ligament tissue for isolating periodontal ligament fibroblasts. Periodontal clinical parameters for tooth

collection were determined based on clinical probing depth and attachment level. Probing depth was measured using a calibrated periodontal probe (Williams Periodontal Probe, Aksim Surgical Ltd, TW3 1EA, UK) from the gingival margin to the base of the probing depth. Attachment level was measured from the base of the probing depth to the cemento-enamel junction. Diseased tooth surfaces involved in the study showed at least a 5mm probing depth and a 5mm clinical attachment loss.

To identify areas of the teeth exposed to the pocket environment, a pencil mark was made at the gingival margin level just before extraction. Extractions were performed under local anesthesia (Mepecaine-L, the Alexandria Co., Alexandria, Egypt), ensuring minimal disturbance to the test areas. After extraction, a fine number 0 round bur (Brassler, Savannah, GA, USA) was used to create a groove at the pencil mark and another groove at the base of the pocket at the most coronal level of periodontal tissue attachment to the root surface. The test areas were then ultrasonically cleaned until hard, sound tooth structure was evident. This procedure was carried out using ultrasonic scalers (Yimei UD-32, Yimei Dentistry Industry Co. Ltd, Zhengzhou, China).

Sample preparation, sterilization, and assignment were performed as follows: Following the method described by Gamal et al. (1998), a horizontal cut was made at the groove level to separate the root from the crown of each tooth while continuously cooling with water. The root was then cut longitudinally through the pulp to the test area's apical point⁽¹⁵⁾. To create a specimen chip, a second horizontal cut was made at the base of the pocket to separate the test area from the tooth. Finally, specimens were stored in sterile saline solution at 4°C and prepared for experiments (Figure 1,)⁽¹⁶⁾.

Figure 1: (A & B) Root Samples

Human Periodontal Ligament Fibroblast Isolation and Culture

Periodontal ligament fibroblasts were prepared in the Central lab of stem cells and biomaterials applied research (CLSBAR) in faculty of dentistry, Ain Shams University.

Periodontal ligament fibroblasts were collected from ten impacted third molars for PDL harvesting and expansion. Under strict aseptic conditions, teeth were extracted and washed several times in biopsy media. A sterile centrifuge tubes containing 10 ml transferring medium was used to transfer the teeth to the lab. Under the sterile atmosphere of a laminar flow chamber tooth was twice cleaned in phosphate-buffered saline (Bio-Whittaker) with 100 µg/mL streptomycin and 100 µ/mL penicillin and teeth roots were scraped with a sterile scalpel (No. 15) in order to collect the periodontal tissues. After that the tissues were cut into 1-2 mm² fragments and digested in 2 mg/mL collagenase IV, 1 mg/ml dispase II and 0.2 µmol/L Eagle's minimum essential medium (Bio-Whittaker Inc., Walkersville, MD, USA) in tissue flask at 37°C for 30 minutes in an incubator. After removal of the first digested cell suspension, tissue was digested again in the same solution and incubated for 90 minutes at 37°C, (Fig.3). After centrifugation, the final tissues were seeded in a 25 cm² tissue culture flask with EMEM comprising 100 µ/mL penicillin and 100 µg/mL streptomycin, 1% amphotericin, 15% fetal bovine serum and 200 µmol/L L-glutamine. Flasks were placed in 5% CO₂ and 95% air in a 37°C humidified incubator. Throughout 24 hours, cells were left to adhere, and the unattached cells were washed with PBS, and fresh medium was placed and refreshed every 3 days. When cell cultures reached 80% confluence, cells were transferred to tissue culture flasks using a solution of 0.05% trypsin and 1 µmol/L EDTA and continuously sub-cultured in the complete growth medium. When confluency was reached in 25 cm² flasks, the cells were pooled into PDL populations and stored at -70°C. Cells from the third passage were used in our study. Phase contrast microscopy was used throughout cell culture methods to track cell growth, and every cell had a shape similar to that of a fibroblast.

Curcumin Paste Preparation

Curcumin paste was Prepared in Nano Gate lab. According to Patwekar et al., ⁽¹⁷⁾ (Patwekar SL, Khavane KB, Chainpure PR, Shivpuje SA. A review on different preparation methods used for development of curcumin nanoparticles. International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts. 2021;9(1):4088-101). Firstly, to prepare 5ml curcumin paste 2% w/v, 0.1 gm of Curcumin powder was suspended in 5ml distilled water with stirring for 30 min, furthermore, 0.25gm Impact of curcumin on tongue ulcer healing in albino of Carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) was sprinkled gently and gradually over the solution under mild temperature at 35°C with vigorous stirring to get homogenous paste. Then to get 5ml curcumin paste 1% w/v, 0.05 gm of Curcumin powder was suspended in 5ml distilled water with stirring for 30 minutes, then 0.25gm of CMC was sprinkled gently and gradually over the solution under mild temperature at 35°C with vigorous stirring to get homogenous paste. Finally, 0.006 gm of Curcumin powder was suspended in 5ml DH₂O to get 0.12 % w/v with stirring for 30 min. furthermore, 0.25gm of CMC was sprinkled gently and gradually over the solution under mild temperature 35°C with vigorous stirring to get homogenous paste ^(14, 15). (Figure 2)

Figure 2: (A) 0.12% Curcumin Gel, (B) 1% Curcumin Gel and (C) 2% Curcumin Gel
Experimental Design

The treated tooth chip samples were randomly distributed into 4 groups (5 teeth segments) according to the treatment protocol. For all groups, PDL cells from ten different subjects were pooled and cultured in an EMEM with 0.5% FBS and PDL cells were counted using a hemocytometer, and 35×10^5 cells/200mL were utilized for each sample. Each sample consisted of diseased root samples seeded with PDL cells following its coating with different concentrations of curcumin. Group 1 (G1), 0.12% of curcumin paste. Group 2 (G2), 1% curcumin paste. Group 3 (G3), 2% curcumin paste. Group 4 (G4), control group with no surface coating. The cells were incubated on the test samples of all groups for 24 h at 37°C in an atmosphere of 95% air and 5% CO₂.

Samples Fixation and SEM Preparation

Following a 24-hour incubation period for the sample segments, the culture media was taken out and the segments were washed with phosphate buffer saline to get rid of any debris, unattached cells, and culture media contents. Within their chamber slides, samples were fixed with ice-cold Glutaraldehyde at 3% (BDH Chemicals, Ltd. Poole, England) for 30 minutes. The specimens were placed in 70% ethyl alcohol (Merck,

Darmstadt, Germany) for 30 min, then in 100% ethyl alcohol for 2 hours, after which it was left overnight in an extra 100% ethyl alcohol.

The following morning, the specimens were immersed for one hour in a solution containing equal parts 100% ethyl alcohol and 100% amyl acetate, and then for two hours in 100% amyl acetate. The samples were subsequently sputter coated with a 200-Å thick coating of gold (S 150 A, Leica, Cambridge, UK) after being dehydrated in the critical point drier (Balzers, FL9496, Liechtenstein). Following that, the specimens were put in the specimen chamber of a scanning electron microscope (Philips x630, Philips, Eindhoven, the Netherlands) for viewing at x750 magnification, and taking photographs at various magnifications. The investigated root specimens ranged in total surface area from 9 to 24 mm². A treatment-blinded examiner (A.Y.G.) screened cell attachment and morphological analysis on periodontally involved root surface.

Data Analysis

Data management and statistical analysis were performed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) (*IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 18.0. Armonk, NY: IBM Corp*). Parametric data were presented as mean ± standard deviation (SD) values and comparisons between groups were performed by ANOVA test, while non-parametric numeric variables were compared by Kruskal Wallis test. Friedman's test was used to study the changes by time in outcomes within each group. P-values ≤0.05 were considered statistically significant. Sample size calculation if groups = 4 was based on the mean difference of cell adhesion on diseased root samples with different curcumin concentration retrieved from previous research. A total number is 20 (5 in each group) is calculated using Epicalc. Program version 1.02 assuming a power of 80 % and alpha=0.05. The sample size is based on Mean ±SD of PDLF on root specimens between G3 and G4 groups was 8.2 ± 1.43 and 6.4± 1.52, respectively ⁽¹⁵⁾.

RESULTS

Morphological Analysis Using Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM):

All samples in group 3 of 2% curcumin concentration showed well defined multilayered adherent cells covering the entire surface with totally flat polyhedral bodies with long cytoplasmic extensions and little or no bacterial colonization or sporadic separate planktonic bacterial adhesion compared to other experimental groups. SEM examination of group 1 (0.12%) samples showed healthy flat and multilayered cell arrangement with evident cytoplasmic extension covering root samples. Bacterial colonization appeared in separate areas in 2 out of the examined samples. SEM examination for group 2 samples (1%) showed similar results to group 1 of a multilayered fibroblastic attached to root samples and scarce bacterial colonization in all samples (Figure 3).

Figure 3: SEM Micrograph of Group 1 Showing Multilayered Healthy Fibroblast Attach to the Root Surface with some Areas of Bacterial Colonization, Magnification (A) 2.00 K X. (B) 5.15 K X

All samples of the control unconditioned group showed predominantly single layer of rounded cells with pulled up and blipped surface which indicate partial loss of cell viability and cellular adhesion. Moreover, the surface was completely covered with bacterial colonies. (Figure 4)

Figure 4: SEM Micrograph of Group 4 showing the Surface area Completely Covered by Rounded cells and Bacterial Colonies, Magnification (A) 5.00 K X. (B) 5.00 K X

DISCUSSION

To the best of the authors' knowledge, the present study was the first study evaluating the efficacy of different concentrations of curcumin on PDL cells adhesion to periodontally affected root surfaces. Root samples were obtained from periodontally affected roots between the gingival margin and the base of the pocket in order to get areas exposed to bacterial environment in the oral cavity and later undergo healing by long junctional epithelium to mimic naturally affected root surfaces after non-surgical scaling and root planing.

In this study, group III (2% curcumin) showed most of the cells exhibited flat polyhedral bodies, with long cytoplasmic extensions denoting maximum cell attachment and minimal bacterial colonization. This was followed by group II (1%) and group I (0.12%) respectively with more round or spindle cells, short cytoplasmic extensions, pulled up morphology and more biofilm surface coverage. This could be attributed to the significant antibacterial effect of 2% curcumin concentration which results in increased root surface energy and improved fibroblast attachment ⁽¹⁸⁾.

Moreover, curcumin itself enhances collagen formation by fibroblast which improve the attachment. This result comes in consistency with a previous in vitro study that reported the effect of curcumin on increasing cellular proliferation and collagen synthesis at wound site with increased DNA and collagen especially type III collagen that improved fibroblast attachment ⁽¹⁹⁾. This study comes parallel with the present study outcomes that curcumin 2% group showed minimal bacterial colonization with strong antibacterial activity against gram-negative bacteria ⁽²⁰⁾.

The antibacterial activity increased with increased concentration of curcumin in group III (2% curcumin). This was consistent with other in vivo study who concluded that 2% curcumin gel as a local delivery in the management of chronic periodontitis had improved clinical parameters such as plaque index (PI), Gingival index (GI), pocket depth (PD) and clinical attachment loss (CAL) due to its antibacterial activity which make it a feasible and productive approach to supplement mechanical debridement as subgingival irritant due to its antibacterial activity ⁽²¹⁾.

The positive outcome of 2% curcumin paste in reducing bacterial colonization in group III may be due to curcumin attachment to bacterial cell wall of periodontal pathogens and ROS production, which can destroy the pathogens in the immediate vicinity ⁽²²⁾. Cell morphology is commonly used to denote the degree of cellular attachment and viability. In the present study curcumin 2% showed more flat cells with long cytoplasmic extension. In an in- vitro study that investigated the effect of laser treatment on fibroblast attachment to root surfaces fibroblasts that were tightly attached to root sections showed numerous lamellipodia and flat in appearance, in comparison with the fibroblasts poorly attached to untreated root sections exhibited few attachment processes and were round in appearance ⁽²³⁾.

Our results in control group with no curcumin coating showed impairment in fibroblast attachment and showed more apparent pulled up appearance with blipped surface.

Additionally, the control group showed the highest bacterial contamination with the least antibacterial activity, and which was also noted with no significant difference than in group I (0.12% curcumin) and group II (1% curcumin). These results may be due to the inadequate antibacterial effect of curcumin 0.12 and 1% leading to the presence of contaminating bacterial endotoxins on root specimens adversely affect the cell adhesion. These results were consistent with other in vitro study which assessed the effect of endotoxin adsorbed to dental surfaces on attachment of human gingival fibroblasts and found that bacterial endotoxin inhibited cell attachment to dental surfaces. Moreover, elimination of bacterial endotoxins had improved the attachment ⁽²⁴⁾.

DECLARATIONS

Ethics Approval and Consent to Participate

It was approved by Research Ethics Committee at Faculty of Dentistry, October 6 University, Giza, Egypt, with approval number (RECO6U/25-2022)

Consent for Publication

Not applicable.

Data availability Statement

The original data are available at corresponding author upon request.

Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Authors Contributions

NB: conception and design of the study; data acquisition and analysis; interpretation of data; manuscript draft and revision; personal accountability, HY: design of the study; interpretation of data; manuscript revision; personal accountability. AF: contributed to data acquisition, analysis, interpretation, drafted and revised manuscript, MW: contributed to data acquisition, analysis, interpretation, drafted and revised manuscript, AG: conception and design of the study; data acquisition and analysis; interpretation of data; manuscript draft and revision; personal accountability. All authors reviewed and approved the manuscript.

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